

**TEACHING THE TECHNIQUE OF ROWING MOVEMENTS AT THE
STAGE OF INITIAL TRAINING IN SYNCHRONIZED SWIMMING.**

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Abstract. The article deals with the issues of initial training in the technique of rowing movements in synchronized swimming. One of the important factors in teaching synchronized swimming is the technically competent mastering of rowing exercises at the initial stage of training. Depending on the level of technically competently mastered movements in the future, a synchronized swimmer can improve them and achieve high results in competitive activities. One of the main goals in teaching rowing movements is to improve existing techniques and include many special exercises.

Key words: Synchronized swimming, vertical and horizontal positions, support stroke, standard stroke, reverse, propeller, canoe, figures, exercises.

Introduction. Synchronized swimming is an actively developing sport. Due to its spectacularity, colorfulness and sportiness, it is cultivated in many countries of the world and is included in the program of the Olympic Games. The constant influx of newcomers to the synchronized swimming section convinces that this sport meets the desire of girls and girls for physical improvement and harmonious development. As a water sport, synchronized swimming instills a number of vital skills. Mastering the technique of synchronized swimming, students receive versatile sports training, as well as learn the elements of choreography, rhythmic gymnastics, acrobatics, and rhythm. All this contributes to the development of motor and general aesthetic culture [1, 4].

A distinctive feature of synchronized swimming is the need to perform vertical and horizontal positions, provided that the hands create constant support on the water.

The aim of the work the study is to improve the methodology for teaching support strokes in synchronized swimming at the stage of initial training.

Research objectives:

1. To study and analyze the special literature to study the characteristics of the support stroke technique for female athletes in synchronized swimming.
2. To develop a set of exercises for targeted training in the elements of synchronized swimming technique in the learning process.
3. To experimentally substantiate the effectiveness of teaching the technique of performing the support stroke in synchronized swimming.

Organization of the experiment: The experiment was organized in three stages. At the first stage (January 2022), special literature on the research topic was studied and analyzed. At the second stage (February 2022), a pedagogical experiment was organized and a specialized set of exercises was tested to teach the technique of support strokes. At the third stage (March 2022), the data obtained during the experiment were processed.

During the analysis of special sources on synchronized swimming, it was found that, in groups of initial training in synchronized swimming for 1 year, they study the technique of synchronized swimming, which includes teaching the technique of basic strokes (flat, standard, reverse), the main positions of synchronized swimming: on the back, on the chest, on the side, tucking, tight tucking, bent over, bending the knee on the chest, on the back. Backstroke: standard stroke, reverse stroke, propeller, reverse propeller. Movement on the chest: reverse stroke, propeller, canoe [2, 5, 6, 8].

The experiment was organized on the basis of the ChSK "Chekhov sport club", it was attended by 20 girls involved in the initial training group of the 1st year of study. Athletes were divided into 2 groups (10 people each) control and experimental. The initial level of physical development, general physical, special physical and technical fitness of female athletes in both groups was the same.

Classes in the control group were conducted according to the methodology recommended for children's youth sports schools and schools of the Olympic reserve [3, 7].

In the training sessions for female athletes of the experimental group, an experimental set of exercises was proposed for targeted training in the technique of performing support strokes in synchronized swimming. From the first lesson, the training process included exercises to create a support with water (for 1–5 lessons); auxiliary exercises when teaching to work with hands in the crawl methods on the chest and on the back; as well as to teach movement in various positions with the help of work with arms and legs, in a horizontal position on the back; work with legs and arms in sports methods of swimming using exercises on the spot, with supporting and auxiliary means and in motion (6-12 lessons).

A set of exercises for purposeful training in the technique of performing a support stroke in synchronized swimming.

Tasks:	Exercises:
<p>Familiarization with the technique of performing support strokes.</p>	<p>Exercises with gymnastic sticks: alternating bending and straightening of the arms, circular movements with a stick from various starting positions; raising the stick up and lowering it behind the head behind the back; stepping over a stick.</p> <p>Exercises with balls: throws with one and two hands, catching with one and two hands from below and from above; throw up with one hand and catch after hitting the floor.</p> <p>Exercises on the gymnastic bench: walking on the bench, stepping over the bench; flexion and extension of the arms; sitting on a bench - raising the legs and tilting the torso; jumping</p>

	<p>from the bench to the right, to the left, legs apart, legs together.</p> <p>Exercises on the gymnastic wall: climbing, hanging with the face, back, angle; standing sideways or facing the wall, bending forward, backward, to the sides; squats on one leg and on two legs</p> <p>Breathing exercises: holding the breath at rest and when performing movements.</p>
<p>Basic stroke training in horizontal and vertical planes (on the spot and on the move):</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lead-in and imitation exercises to get acquainted with the technique of backstroke; - alternating stroke with the right and left hands; - strokes: flat, standard, reverse, "propeller", "canoe", "dolphin", "lobster"; - positions: "on the back", "on the side", "on the chest", "with the leg bent at the knee" only with support. - performing a support stroke in various positions (vertical and horizontal grouping, horizontally on the chest and on the back); - performing movements with the help of support strokes. - vary the technique of strokes (in amplitude, pace); - perform simple transitions with the help of a support stroke (from the grouping position to the "on the back" position and others);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - perform 180 and 360° tuck turns, somersaults. - performing a support stroke in its middle part in the crawl method on the chest; - perform a backstroke in combination with the work of the legs in the crawl on the back; - perform the "canoe" exercise in combination with the work of the legs in the front crawl method.
<p>Maintaining the vertical position of the body in the water (head up) and movement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in this position, rowing movements with legs are used - "ekbite" (modification of breaststroke movements with legs): - rowing movements with legs: "ekbite" in forward and backward movement; - the simplest figures of synchronized swimming: "rotation in the tuck", "turn back in the tuck". <p>Simulation exercises on land:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the main positions of synchronized swimming (on the back, on the chest, on the side, grouping, on the back with a bent knee, angle up); - special strokes (standard stroke, reverse stroke, propeller, canoe, support stroke).

Before the start of the experiment, as well as at the end, we took special tests to determine the level of general physical, special physical and technical fitness of synchronized swimmers (see Tables 1-3).

Table 1.
**Indicators of the general physical fitness of female athletes on land before
and after the experiment**

Indicators	Control group (x)		differen ce	Experimental group (x)		differen ce
	before	after		before	after	
Lying on your back go to a sitting position (times)	4	6	+2	4	12	+8
Lying on your back raise your legs to touch the floor behind your head (times)	4	8	+4	3,4	14	+11,6
Lean forward with legs grip (hold sec	5	10	+5	5	24	+19
Jumping up from a deep squat (time)	4	10	+6	4	18	+14

As can be seen from the data shown in Table 1, in the test "Lying on your back, go to a sitting position" at the end of the experiment, the average indicator in the control group was 6 times, and in the experimental group 12 times, which is twice as good as the indicator of the control group. In the test "Lying on the back, lifting the legs to touch the floor behind the head", the average indicator in the control group was 8 times, and in the experimental group 14 times. In the test "Bend forward with leg grip" the average in the control group was 10 seconds, and in the experimental 24 seconds. In the test "Jumping up from a deep squat", the average score in the control group was 10 times, and in the experimental group 18 times.

Table 2.

Indicators of special physical training of female athletes on land before and after the experiment

Indicators	Control group (x)		Experimental group (x)	
	before	after	before	after
Twines (cm):				
-left	-	10	-	4
-right	-	10	-	4
-straight	-	20	-	2
Gymnastic bridge (sm)	-	60	-	32
Stand on the shoulder blades (perform technically correct)	-	3	-	4,5
Handstand (with insurance) (perform technically correct)	-	2,8	-	4
Side flip right, left (perform technically correct)	-	3	-	5
Standing in choreographic positions (perform technically correct)	-	3	-	4,5
Forward roll (perform technically correct)	-	3	-	5
Raising and abducting a straight leg 90 degrees (forward, side, back) (perform technically correct)	-	3	-	4,5
Stand on toes hands down - up, eyes closed (c)	-	5	-	14

To assess the level of special physical training of athletes, the tests were chosen: longitudinal and transverse splits, gymnastic bridge, stand on the shoulder blades, stand on the hands, side flip to the right and left, stand in choreographic positions, somersault forward, raising and abducting the straight leg by 90 degrees, standing on socks hands down - up, eyes closed. As can be seen from the data in the table in all tests, the average performance of female athletes in the experimental group significantly exceeds the average performance of female athletes in the control group. This suggests that the set of exercises proposed by us also contributes to the development of general and special preparedness of young synchronized swimmers.

Table 3.

**Indicators of technical training on the water of female athletes on land
before and after the experiment**

Показатели	Control group (x)		Experimental group (x)	
	before	after	before	after
Agbit walking 12.5m (point)	-	3	-	3,5
Swimming (standard stroke, reverse, propeller, canoe) 25m (point)	-	3	-	4,5
Execution of the simplest figures for evaluation (point)	-	3	-	4
Swimming in positions (point):		3		
- angle up one 25m	-		-	4,5
- angle up with two 12.5m	-		-	4,5
-flamingo 15m	-		-	4
Execution of figures of the compulsory program (by lottery) (point)	-	3	-	4,5
Control execution of combination exercises (point) (perform technically correctly)	-	3	-	4,5

To assess the level of technical training of athletes, walking tests in "agbite", swimming (standard stroke, reverse, propeller, canoe), execution of the simplest figures, swimming in the positions of an angle up one, an angle up two and flamingos, the performance of figures of the compulsory program, control performance of combination exercises. The average performance of synchronized swimmers in the experimental group significantly differs from that of athletes in the control group. The scores given for the technique of performing vault strokes are 1.5 points higher, which in turn had a positive effect on the technique of performing positions and figures of the compulsory program in which there is a vault stroke. The use of the set of exercises proposed by us for targeted training in the technique of performing support strokes contributed to the technically competent mastering of the elements and figures of synchronized swimming, the performance of which requires strokes: standard, reverse propeller and canoe.

Conclusions:

1. The indicators of the backstroke technique in synchronized swimming are determined by the peculiarities of the positions. In more complex positions (“up angle” and “two up angle”) the stroke amplitude in the vertical and horizontal directions is much shorter, respectively, the speed of the hand movement and the rate of movements are higher than in the “on the back” position.

2. After using a set of exercises to teach the technique of support strokes, a qualitative change in the stroke technique is observed: the vertical displacement of the hand decreases, thereby providing the necessary continuous support on the water.

3. Propulsion systems used in practice in the process of learning and improving the technique of synchronized swimming are differentiated by beginners in terms of complexity and method of their implementation. The group of tasks for changing the stroke amplitude is the most accessible for most athletes, regardless of their age and qualifications. More difficult for beginners is the group of tasks to change the pace of rowing movements.

4. Parallel use of various elements of synchronized swimming and traditional means of teaching sports swimming contributes to a better mastering of the technique.

5. The proposed experimental methodology for initial training in the technique of performing a support stroke in synchronized swimming using appropriate propulsion systems provides high-quality and accelerated mastering of the technical elements of synchronized swimming.

Practical recommendations:

1. Start learning strokes and positions at the same time as learning sports swimming techniques.

2. It is recommended to include exercises aimed at teaching the backstroke to the group of water mastery exercises.

3. To activate a conscious approach to mastering the technique, it is advisable to introduce mental “pronunciation” of tasks, performing exercises to music without prior demonstration, into classes.

4. It is advisable to include exercises in pairs with mutual control and mutual evaluation.

5. Perform positions and strokes in pairs (synchronously), in triplets and so on; under the account, with musical accompaniment; bundles of position in place and in motion.

6. To maintain the emotional background, use the game form of conducting classes more often; after mastering a number of positions, make planar ligaments; give athletes the task to independently compose ligaments for 16-36 counts to the music.

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